

Combined Modeling Approach to Study the Interaction of a Cold Plasma Jet with Solid Tumors

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During the past decade, computer modeling of atmospheric pressure plasma jets (APPJs) has attracted scientific attention. Particularly, several plasma fluid models (PFM) have been developed, involving commercially-available software [1] or in-house codes [2], which have provided significant insight of plasma propagation mechanisms, production pathways of reactive oxygen and nitrogen species (RONS), electric field dynamics, and plasma interaction with solid/liquid targets. Combining computer models with targeted experiments, invaluable information can be obtained for the optimization of APPJs and their implementation in plasma medicine and cancer therapy [3]. Therefore, modeling the effect of APPJs on solid tumors may offer promise in designing novel synergistic therapies (e.g., plasma with nanomedicine [4]). The present study proposes a novel multiphysics/multiscale modeling approach that combines a PFM using COMSOL Multiphysics[®] [1] and a cutting-edge in-silico framework for cancer modelling, FEB3 [4]. The PFM will determine the RONS and electric fields from a He APPJ interacting with a solid tumor, which will then be injected into FEB3 (see Fig. 1). FEB3 simulates drug transport and their effects on tumors (see Fig. 1). In this work, however, tumors will be exposed to plasma RONS (and/or drugs). This approach will allow us to interrogate how plasma components by themselves and in combination with chemotherapy drugs propagate through biological tissue. The proposed methodology is very innovative and is expected to shed light on the role of plasma for the treatment of cancerous lesions.

Fig. 1 APPJ-tumor interaction simulation (PFM, left) provides RONS densities on solid tumor surface. RONS (alone or in synergy with drugs) diffusion in the tumor is subsequently simulated (middle/right).

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References

- [1] C. Lazarou *et al.*, *Plasma Sources Sci. Technol.*, **27**, 105007 (2018).
- [2] S. A. Norberg *et al.*, *J. Appl. Phys.*, **118**, 013301 (2015).
- [3] W. Murphy *et al.*, *J. Phys. D: Appl. Phys.*, **47**, 472001 (2014).
- [4] P. A. Wijeratne *et al.*, *Interface Focus*, **9**:20180063 (2019).